

DISCRIMINATING PERSISTENT AND VARIABLE HYDRATION COMPONENTS ON THE MOON USING M³ HYPERSPECTRAL DATA. J. L. Bishop¹, C. Wöhler², K. S. Wohlfarth², M. R. D. Gruendler^{1,3}, C. Tokubo^{1,4}, K. A. Wilk⁵, M. Parente⁶, J. Flahaut⁷, R. L. Klima⁸, T. Panambur⁶, T. Sander², ¹SETI Institute (Mountain View, CA, USA, jbishop@seti.org), ²Technische Universität Dortmund (Dortmund, Germany), ³University of California San Diego (La Jolla, CA, USA), ⁴University of California Davis (Davis, CA, USA), ⁵Brown University (Providence, RI, USA), ⁶University of Massachusetts Amherst (Amherst, MA), ⁷Université de Lorraine, CRPG (Vandœuvre-lès-Nancy, France), ⁸Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Lab (Laurel, MD, USA).

Introduction: Our analyses of Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³) spectra indicate two distinct forms of hydration in the lunar regolith that vary with location across the moon and time of day. Previous studies identified a hydration feature near 2.7-3 μm that could include components from OH and H₂O [e.g., 1, 2, 3]. Revised thermal emission corrections based on Diviner, Gaofen-4, and MERTIS data enabled mapping global trends in lunar surface hydration with time of day (Fig. 1)[4]. Correlation of M³ spectra from mare and highlands regions with lab spectra subsampled for M³ channels [5] reveals differences in the diurnal changes in shape of the hydration band.

Methods: *M³ Global Dataset.* Spectral parameter maps (Fig. 2) [6] were derived from recently calibrated M³ global images [4] and correlated with lunar elemental abundance maps [6] and mineral abundance maps [7]. Analyses of these 20 pixel per degree spectral parameter maps from different times of day demonstrate two distinct hydration components – one that varies with composition across the surface of the Moon, and another one that varies with time of day [4]. Spectra were collected from 5 regions of the moon (Fig. 3) where data were available for both the morning and midday times (Fig. 1). These 5 spectra were ratioed from morning to midday to visualize changes in the hydration band intensity and shape with time of day (Figs. 4-5).

Fig. 1 Integrated band depth (IBD-3 μm) maps for the hydration feature near 3 μm for morning and mid-day derived from 20 pixel per degree M³ imagery [4].

Lab Spectra Subsampling. Reflectance spectra from 0.4-3 μm were selected from the Bishop spectral library, the USGS spectral library, and a recent study of anorthosite [8] (Fig. 1). The lab spectra were first convolved to the M³ targeted channels from 0.4460 to 2.9912 μm at ~ 10 nm intervals. Next we converted the subsampled targeted spectra to the lower spectral resolution of the M³ global channels by averaging 4 channels using step sizes of 4 for most of the spectrum and step sizes of 2 near the 1 μm region, as set up by the M³

instrument team to better document the Fe-bearing silicate components [1].

Fig. 2 Morning IBD-3 μm map for central region of the Moon containing mare and highlands material [1] Blue indicates higher hydration levels.

Fig. 3 Albedo map for the same region in Fig. 2 showing locations of M³ spectra analyzed in this study. Spectra 1, 3, and 5 were collected at brighter highlands regions and spectra 2 and 4 were collected at darker mare regions for both lunar morning and lunar midday times.

Results. Spectra 2 and 4 collected in the lunar morning (6:00-8:00 AM) from the darker mare region exhibit a notable pyroxene band near 1 μm and a weak band near 2.3 μm . An average spectrum collected from pyroxene-rich regions [4,6] is similar to the spectrum from region 4 (Fig. 4). Spectra 1, 3, and 5 were also collected from a lunar morning image, but from the brighter highlands regions that do not exhibit notable pyroxene features (Fig. 4). An average spectrum collected from low-pyroxene regions [4,6] is similar to the spectrum from region 3 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. M^3 spectra from 5 regions. Spectra collected in the lunar morning from 5 locations in Fig. 3 (triangle symbols). Average spectra from low- and high-pyroxene regions (circle symbols) are similar to spectra from region 3 and region 4, respectively. Solid lines mark selected M^3 channels in the hydration region. Broken lines mark pyroxene features.

Ratios of selected M^3 spectra were conducted to assist in evaluating spectral trends. One ratio was prepared for the average pyroxene-rich spectrum compared to the average pyroxene-poor spectrum. This illustrates increasing pyroxene bands near 1.03 and 2.3 μm , as well as a drop in reflectance near 2.9 μm (Fig. 5), indicating that the pyroxene-bearing regions are more hydrated. Morning to midday spectral ratios were determined to better visualize changes near 2.7–3 μm due to hydration features. The pyroxene-rich mare spectra (2,4) have stronger IBD-3 μm values than the corresponding highlands spectra (1,3,5) in the morning M^3 image (Fig. 2), indicating elevated hydration in the lunar morning for the mare regions. The morning to midday ratio spectra for the darker mare locations (2,4) illustrate a large drop in reflectance at 2.7 μm (Fig. 5), supporting significant change in this feature from morning to midday [2]. In contrast, the morning to midday ratio spectra for the highlands regions (1,3,5) exhibit a smaller change in hydration. These results suggest that one form of hydration is always present on the lunar surface, potentially represented by midday mare spectra. A second form of hydration changes with time of day, where the change in hydration is smaller for highlands regions and larger for mare regions.

Besides the difference in abundance of hydration, we noticed changes in the spectral shape near 2.7–3 μm (Fig. 6). The mare region ratio spectra (2,4) drop in reflectance gradually and continue to decrease to the end of the M^3 channels, similar to spectra of anorthite (Fig. 6A). In contrast, the highlands ratio spectra decrease more rapidly near 2.8–2.9 μm and then flatten or even increase in reflectance at the end of the M^3 channels, more similar to spectra of olivine, pyroxene, and volcanic glass (Fig. 6B). These differences in shape of the hydration feature in morning to midday ratio spectra further support the idea that two forms of hydration are present in the lunar regolith.

Fig. 5. M^3 ratio spectra to highlight changes with time and location. **Top)** Ratios of spectra collected in the lunar morning to spectra collected at midday from 5 locations in Fig. 3. **Bottom)** Ratio of the average spectrum of high-pyroxene regions to the average spectrum from low-pyroxene regions from Fig. 4. Lines mark spectral features of interest.

Fig. 6. Ratioed M^3 spectra compared to convolved analog spectra. **A)** Ratios of morning to midday spectra from pyroxene-rich dark regions 2 and 4 from Fig. 3 compared to anorthite spectra. **B)** Ratios of morning to midday spectra from bright regions 1, 3, and 5 from Fig. 3 compared to spectra of olivine, pyroxene, and volcanic glass. Gray lines mark selected M^3 channels in the hydration region.

Acknowledgements: Support from NASA LDAP grant #80NSSC21K1480 and the SETI Institute Frontier Development Lab are greatly appreciated.

References: [1] Pieters C.M. et al. (2009) *Science*, 326, 568-572. [2] Wöhler C. et al. (2017) *Sci. Adv.*, 3, e1701286. [3] Li & Milliken (2017) *Sci. Adv.*, 3, e1701471. [4] Wohlfarth K.S. et al. (2023) *A&A*, 674, A69. [5] Bishop J.L. et al. (2025) *Eur. Lunar Symp.*, Muenster, Abstract. [6] Wohlfarth K.S. et al. (2024) *AGU Fall Mtg*, #P41C-02. [7] Arnaud M. et al. (2020) *LPS LI*, Abstract #3008. [8] Wilk K. A. et al. (2025) *Icarus*, 411, 115945.